

A Kinetic Study of the Oxidation Reaction of L-Cysteine by Potassium Hexacyanoferrate(III) in Aqueous Acidic Medium

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Kinetics of oxidation of L-cysteine by one-electron oxidant, potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) have been investigated spectrophotometrically at 420 nm as a function of temperature, pH and ionic strength. The rate data indicate first order dependence each in $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$ and $[\text{Cys}]$. The reactive species of cysteine are neutral cysteine and protonated cysteine. The effect of ionic strength on the reaction has little effect. The activation parameters ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger have also been calculated. The results support for an associative mechanism for the reaction.

Several reports are available in the literature on the reaction of organic and inorganic substrates with potassium hexacyanoferrate(III)¹. In the present communication, we report the oxidation of N, O and S containing amino acid like L-cysteine by potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) in aqueous acidic medium.

Results and Discussion

The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) are evaluated for the reaction at different temperatures and at constant pH and ionic strength from the slopes of $\log [(A_\infty - A_0)/(A_\infty - A_t)]$ vs time plots. The second order rate constant (k_2) are calculated from k_{obs} values (Table 1).

TABLE 1—VALUES OF k_{obs} FOR THE OXIDATION REACTION OF CYSTEINE BY $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$ AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND $[\text{Cys}]$

$[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = 5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 1.5 \pm 0.1$, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$
(NaClO_4), $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 420 \text{ nm}$

$10^3 [\text{Cys}]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$		
	30°	40°	45°
5.0	5.0	7.2	8.89
7.5	6.0	12.6	16.4
10.0	7.0	20.3	25.5
15.0	10.4	33.7	43.2
$k_f (\times 10^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$	6.5 ± 0.05	13.5 ± 0.05	23.5 ± 0.05

The slopes of the linear plots of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $\log [\text{cys}]$ for all temperatures are unity. This indicates

that the order of reaction with respect to $[\text{cys}]$ is unity. The k_{obs} values were also calculated at different $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$ concentrations, i.e. (2, 3, 4 and 5) $\times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, but at fixed $[\text{cysteine}]$ ($5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), $\text{pH} = 1.5 \pm 0.1$, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and temperature = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. These values are nearly constant ($k_{\text{obs}} = 3.15 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$). This observation indicates that the rate of reaction follows first order dependence in $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$. So, the rate law for reaction is given by equation (1),

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] [\text{cys}]_T \quad (1)$$

Here the concentration term $[\text{cys}]_T$ involves all protonated and unprotonated form of cysteine.

The reaction was followed as a function of pH in the pH range 1.5–3.8. The values of k_{obs} are compiled in Table 2. The pK value of cysteine is 1.71, so the cysteine molecule exists in the neutral form $[\text{cys}]$ and protonated form $[\text{cys H}^+]$. The rate constant plotted against pH resembles the S-type, pH profile for acid-base titration curve. This suggests that one of the reactants involved is like an acid-base equilibrium in the pH range studied. Hence the rate law and the reaction scheme can be written as

Thus the rate law based on the above mechanism is given by equation (5),

$$-d [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] / dt = k_f [\text{Cys} + \text{Cys H}^+] [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) can be further simplified to equation (6),

$$d [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] / dt = k_1 [\text{Cys}] [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] + k_2 [\text{Cys H}^+] [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] \quad (6)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are the rate constants due to the reaction of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ with $[\text{Cys}]$ and $[\text{Cys H}^+]$. On comparing equations (5) and (6), we get

$$k_f = \frac{k_1 [\text{Cys}] + k_2 [\text{Cys H}^+]}{[\text{Cys}] + [\text{Cys H}^+]} \quad (7)$$

when one of the forms predominates over the other in the experimental pH range due to its higher reactivity. In this situation only one limiting rate constant is obtained. Thus if $[\text{Cys}] \gg [\text{Cys H}^+]$, equation (7) is reduced to equation (8),

$$k_f = k_1 + k_2 \frac{[\text{Cys H}^+]}{[\text{Cys}]} \quad (8)$$

Considering the equilibrium,

and using equation (9), equation (8) can be transformed to equation (10),

$$k_f = k_1 + k_2 K [\text{H}^+] \quad (10)$$

If $[\text{Cys H}^+] \gg [\text{Cys}]$, equation (7) is arranged as

$$k_f = k_1 \frac{[\text{Cys}]}{[\text{Cys H}^+]} + k_2 \quad (11)$$

$$k_f = \frac{k_1}{K [\text{H}^+]} + k_2 \quad (12)$$

The plot of k_f vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$ yielded a straight line having positive slope and positive intercept. The plot of k_f vs $[\text{H}^+]$ is not a straight line. Thus the actual rate law is given by equation (11) and dominated form of cysteine is the protonated cysteine in the experimental pH range. The intercept of k_f versus $1/[\text{H}^+]$ plot gives the value of k_2 ($2.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) and slope gives the value of k_1 ($6.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$). The value of k_2 is much higher than k_1 value because the protonated species $[\text{Cys H}^+]$ is dominant and more reactive in comparison to neutral cysteine $[\text{Cys}]$. So the reaction (4) is fast and reaction (3) is slow and rate-determining one.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF k_{obs} FOR THE OXIDATION OF CYSTEINE BY $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ AT DIFFERENT pH

$[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = 5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Cys}] = 5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO₄), temp. = $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$, $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 420 \text{ nm}$

pH	$10^3 k_{\text{obs}}$	$k_f (\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$
1.5	0.50	0.10
2.0	2.05	0.41
2.5	5.25	1.05
3.0	17.40	3.48
3.3	26.80	5.36
3.7	28.40	5.68

Ionic strength has no effect on the rate of reaction. This is because one of the reactants is the neutral cysteine in the rate-determining state while the other is negatively charged ferricyanide ($Z_A Z_B = 0$). This also supports our earlier conclusion that the neutral cysteine is reacting in the rate-determining step (eqn. 3). The values of activation parameters, i.e. E_a , ΔH^* and ΔS^* evaluated using Eyring's plot and Arrhenius equation, are given in Table 1. These values support for an associative mechanism for the reaction.

Lastly, a repetitive spectral scan was recorded as a function of time (Fig. 1). Three distinct peaks were observed at 280, 309 and 420 nm. These peaks are due to $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ and their peak heights decreased with time due to its conversion to $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$. We could not observe the peak due

Fig. 1. Repetitive scan for the reaction mixture during a kinetic run at a 30° : (A) 0, (B) 5, (C) 10, (D) 20, (E) 30 and (F) 60 min; $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = 5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Cys}] = 7.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO_4)

to any intermediate because of its transient existence and very low concentration. The peak due to the formation of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ could not also be observed because of its featureless spectrum both in uv and visible region.

Experimental

$\text{K}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ (B.D.H.), L-cysteine (Loba), NaClO_4 (E. Merck) and HClO_4 (B.D.H.) were of analytical grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout. The ionic strength was maintained by using NaClO_4 .

A Toshniwal CL-46 pH meter was used and standardised before use by using standard buffers (B.D.H.). The temperature of reactants was maintained by a self-designed thermostat. Spectral scan was recorded on a Shimadzu UV-240 spectro-

photometer. The progress of reaction was followed by the decrease in the absorbance at 420 nm (λ_{max} of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$) using a Spectronic 20 spectrophotometer (Milton Roy and Company, U.S.A.) equipped with a circulatory arrangement for thermostating the cell compartment. The reaction was carried out in stoppered Jena volumetric flask and the temperature of each reactant was equilibrated for at least 0.5 h before mixing. The sample quenching method was adopted for measuring the absorbance. The reaction was followed under pseudo-first order condition by taking large concentration of cysteine. The values of pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were evaluated from the slopes of $\log [(A_{\infty} - A_0)/(A_{\infty} - A_t)]$ vs time plots, where A_0 , A_t and A_{∞} are the absorbances at zero, at time t and at infinite time.

Identification of products : After completion of the reaction, FeCl_3 solution was added to the reaction mixture when a prussian blue colour was obtained. This confirmed the formation of ferrocyanide ion as one of the products during the course of reaction. The ferricyanide ion is thus reduced to ferrocyanide ion. The ninhydrin test was performed and was negative. This proved the absence of free L-cysteine in the product. The oxidised product of L-cysteine was found to be L-cysteine in solution. The presence of ferrocyanide as a product in the solution was further confirmed by ammonium molybdate test².

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